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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE EFFICACY OF ANTIBIOTIC
PROPHYLAXIS GIVEN IN A SINGLE DOSE VERSUS 24-
HOURS AGAINST SURGICAL SITE INFECTIONS**¹Dr . Asma Ishfaq, ²Dr.Muhammad Farhan¹women medical officer mayo hospital Lahore, ²Quaid E Azam Medical College Bahawlpur.**Abstract:**

Objective: To observe the effect of a single dose antibiotic, its efficacy as a 24-hour regimen to prevent SSIs in contaminated, elective surgical procedures and clean procedures.

Study design: A randomized, prospective study.

Place and Duration: In the Surgical Unit I of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from September 2017 to September 2018.

Methods: 208 total cases planned for general surgery were selected for the analysis. Into 2 groups, Patients were divided randomly. A single dose group were given ceftriaxone 2 grams intravenously, while the 24-hour group were given ceftriaxone 2 grams intravenously during anesthesia induction, followed by 8 and 16 hours of 1 g operation.

Results: Ceftriaxone administration in a single-dose regimen was associated with a higher SSI ratio compared to the rates of patients receiving a 24-hour regimen (9.6%, 6.7%).

Conclusion: In the case of clean contaminated and contaminated procedures, multiple prophylactic antibiotic doses should be used for 24 hours instead of the single dose in surgical prophylaxis.

Key Words: Antibiotic prophylaxis, Surgical site infection (SSI).

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INTRODUCTION:

During surgery main problem is Surgical site infections (SSI). It is third most commonly reported nosocomial infection and constitutes more than one-fifth of all medical care-associated infections. SSI is increasing the financial costs on patients and hospitals, but is also an important reason of postoperative mortality and morbidity. The advantages of preoperative antimicrobial prophylaxis in SSTs prevention are demonstrated clearly. Many surgical hospitals suggest multidose prophylaxis of antibiotics, which lasts for 24 to 48 hours and stops until all drainage tubes are discarded. In surgical chemoprophylaxis, antimicrobials improper use leads to a greater infection rate in the surgical site. Antibiotics unnecessary use also results in increased costs, undesirable side effects of drugs, multidrug-resistant infections and resistant strains. There is insufficient proof in the literature about the efficacy, profitability and safety of single-dose prophylaxis; It has been reported that resistance to the associated antibiotics has been reduced and that there are fewer problems in the superinfections and toxicity of drugs. However, there is no consensus on antibiotic prophylaxis in the use of a single dose or multiple doses. Our hospital antibiotic prophylaxis includes 24 hours post-operative antibiotics following pre-operative antibiotics. Most surgeons not use a single dose of prophylaxis in a contaminated and clean contaminated operation for many causes, including skepticism in optimal techniques of sterilization in private and public hospitals. The aim was to decrease the antibiotics use and to introduce the proper guidelines for antibiotic prophylaxis in clean and contaminated general surgical procedures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This randomized, prospective study was held in the Surgical Unit I of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from September 2017 to September 2018. All, more than 18 years, the adult patient was initially included in the study when planned clean, dirty and contaminated elective general surgery. 466 patients were included in the study and 38 patients were excluded because of antibiotic prophylaxis. Patients with active infection were excluded from those who did not want to be part of the study, and those who were already taking antibiotics for the unrelated emergency surgical procedures for diseases. They were also excluded when patients with concomitant

diseases such as diabetes mellitus, anemia, malignancy, etc. Informed consent was obtained for all participants. Into two groups, patients were divided using random sequential method. The one group received two grams of intravenous ceftriaxone (Getofin®) during the induction of anesthesia (Getofin®), while the group received two grams of ceftriaxone for 24 hours (Getofin®) at the time of intravenous administration of 8 and 16 hours after 1 g of surgery and then induction of anesthesia. In the openings or procedures related to the gastrointestinal genitourinary region were added 120 mg of metronidazole and gentamicin 120 mg respectively to the ground. On an elective list, all patients were operated. The surgical site was shaved in the theater, povidone was applied to isolate the study area of the skin prepared with iodine and sterile drapes. With subcuticular suture all wounds were approximated or staple or interrupted prolene and covered with gauze. From the fourth postoperative day to the discharged, patients were evaluated and examined by a doctor doing research every day for up to thirty five days after the operation. Pain in the operation area, permanent fire > 38 ° C, erythema of the wound, sensitivity, wound secretion and separation were taken as SSI symptoms. An empirical antibiotic treatment was initiated for all patients with SSI, considering the bacterial culture results and the sensitivity of the wound currents. The hospital discharge was decided according to the quality of the operation and ranged 1-8 days. Using SPSS 18.0 all data was analyzed. Using chi-square test, both groups were compared. The p value was <0.05 was taken significant statistically.

RESULTS:

During the study duration, 246 patients were included in the analysis and 38 were discontinued or excluded due to non-compliance with the randomized prophylactic antibiotic regimen. 208 total patients participate in the study. The men were 97 and women were 111. The 34.7 years (range, 18-69 years) was the mean age. A single dose ceftriaxone was given in 104 patients and for 24 hours in 104 cases. Both groups are homogeneous and comparable in terms of clinical features and demographic profiles. 17 (8.2%) had SSI from the 208 cases. 10(9.6%) total SSIs was noted in a single dose group and in a 24-hour group 7 (6.7%) of cases had SSIs (p = .004). Table I shows the related infection rate of surgical procedures.

TABLE I: INFECTION RATES IN VARIOUS SURGERIES (n=208)

Operations Performed	No. Performed (%)	No. Infected (%)
Clean contaminated		
Inguinal hernioplasty	36 (33.3)	1 (5.8)
Laprascopic cholecystectomy	32 (15.4)	2 (11.7)
Firoadenoma	31 (14.9)	0 (0)
Open cholecystectomy	21 (10.9)	1 (5.8)
Subtotal thyroidectomy	15 (7.2)	1 (5.8)
Excision of lymph nodes / Sebaceous cyst / ganglion / lipoma	15 (7.2)	0 (0)
Appendicectomy	13 (6.2)	3 (17.6)
Flush ligation / stripping of great saphenous vein	03 (1.4)	0 (0)
Ureterolithotomy	03 (1.4)	1 (5.8)
Pleomorphic adenoma	02 (0.9)	0 (0)
Splenectomy	02 (0.9)	0 (0)
Nephrectomy	01 (0.5)	0 (0)
Tracheostomy	01 (0.5)	0 (0)
Contaminated		
Right hemicolectomy	09 (4.3)	5 (29.4)
Resection and anastomosis	08 (3.8)	2 (11.7)
Exploratory laparotomy	08 (3.8)	0 (0)
Pyelolithotomy	06 (2.8)	1 (5.8)
Gastrojejunostomy	02 (0.9)	0 (0)

Table II shows the recurrence of infections in two groups.

TABLE II: DISTRIBUTION OF INFECTIONS ACCORDING TO THE ANTIBIOTIC REGIMEN

Procedure	Single Dose antibiotics (n=10)	24-hour antibiotics (n=07)
Inguinal hernioplasty	1	-
Laparoscopic cholecystectomy	1	1
Open cholecystectomy	1	-
Subtotal thyroidectomy	1	-
Appendicectomy	2	1
Ureterolithotomy	-	1
Right hemicolectomy	3	2
Resection & anastomosis	-	2
Pyelolithotomy	1	-
Total	10 (9.6 %)	07 (6.7 %)

In two groups (p 0.05, Table III), pathogens isolated were similar taken from SSIs.

TABLE III: FREQUENCY OF VARIOUS PATHOGENS CAUSING SURGICAL SITE INFECTION

Organisms	No. of isolates (%)
Staphylococcus epidermidis	6 (35.3)
Staphylococcus aureus	2 (11.7)
E. coli	3 (17.6)
Proteus	2 (11.7)
Mixed infection	4 (23.5)

(n=17)

DISCUSSION:

Surgical site infection (SSI) remains the main cause of complications postoperatively. The incidence varies between 2.6% and 42.09% worldwide. In this study, the overall infection rate of the surgical site was 7.9%. The optimal antibiotic prophylaxis duration is controversial. Several regimens can range from single doses to multiple doses in a few days. In the case of clean contaminated and contaminated cases, we believe that a single-dose regimen is as effective as a 24-hour regimen to prevent SSI, despite the general consensus of postoperative antibiotics for 24 hours. The role of prophylactic antibiotic therapy in non-apical appendicitis remains controversial. Nooyen et al. In a study comparing a single dose and prophylactic antibiotic therapy for 3 days, he concluded that a single

prophylactic antibiotic dose was as effective as a 3-day course in the prevention of SSI. Eduardo et al. In a prospective randomized clinical trial of 1027 patients undergoing heart surgery, verify that a single prophylactic antibiotic dose is effective because SSI is as effective as 24-hour antibiotics. In this study, 104 patients were given a single dose of ceftriaxone for induction of anesthesia. Another group of 104 patients received three doses of prophylactic antibiotics during anesthesia induction and 8 and 16 hours after surgery. Ceftriaxone administration in a single-dose regimen was associated with a higher SSI rate compared to the rate of patients receiving a 24-hour regimen (9.6% and 6.7%). The study confirms that gram-positive cocci, especially *S. epidermidis*, followed by *S. aureus* are the most common organisms that cause ISE. These

findings are supported by other similar studies confirming gram-positive organisms responsible for most SSIs worldwide. Therefore, in clean and contaminated clean procedures, prophylactic antibiotics that do not violate intestinal integrity should be given against skin organisms. However, operations involving opening of the biliary, urinary tract or GIT should include 2nd-generation cephalosporin.

CONCLUSION:

We concluded that, in clean and contaminated procedures, multiple prophylactic antibiotic doses should be used for 24 hours instead of a single dose in surgical prophylaxis.

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